

Monkey Pox: A re-emerging trans-boundary disease

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Monkey pox is a zoonotic sylvatic pathogen presenting with maculopapular rashes in the palms of the hands and soles of the feet. Although a self-limiting disease, its recent surge in outbreaks is concerning. “*Spill over*” diseases from animals to humans, has seen fold amplification in the last decade. Such zoonotic diseases being multi-factorial require extensive epidemiological analysis for suitable prevention strategies.

History

The mystery of monkey pox (MPX) began with a dog. A three-year-old girl bitten by a prairie dog had symptoms of cellulitis, fever, ocular discharge, lymphadenopathy and papular skin lesions. Even suspected to be a gram-negative bacillus causing tularemia or plague, the organism was subsequently found to be an orthopox virus under negative-stain electron microscopy. Tracing back, the dog was known to be housed close to exotic African rodents such as rope squirrels, tree squirrels, Gambian giant rats, brush-tailed porcupines, dormice and striped mice, which are vectors of MPX.

Earliest discovery of Monkey pox was in 1958 in laboratory monkeys, soon after the eradication of small pox, later found in zoos. Later in 1970, Human monkey pox known to be endemic to central and western African countries was reported. Although most concentrated in the Democratic Republic of Congo, the largest outbreak of MPX was reported in Zaire between 1996 and 1997. Soon after, the first MPX outbreak outside of Africa was reported in the United States of America, linked to contact with infected pet prairie dogs in 2003. After a gap, sporadic outbreaks have been noticed since 2017 and the most recent being in non- endemic countries. Recent reports from India have shed light onto this re-emerging disease.

Drivers of transmission

Currently, two genetically distinct clades have been identified, the Congo Basin (CB) clade and the West African (WA) clade, where the former has been identified in human-to-human transmission. As with any zoonotic disease, natural reservoir hosts play a major role in infection. Here, rodents are suspected to be natural reservoirs in endemic countries, as evidenced by infection in tree squirrels, rope squirrels, Gambian pouched rats, dormice, monkeys etc. However, in non-endemic countries, reservoir hosts are unknown, the recent outbreak may be due to infection surge in endemic regions and its exportation to other countries owing to the global increase in cultural, economic, political relations.

Transmission occurs through direct contact with blood, bodily fluids, or cutaneous or mucosal lesions or bush meat from infected hosts. Respiratory secretions, skin lesions, placenta (congenital form), or during birth or contaminated objects can be source of infection.

Socio- demographical factors play a role in transmission. The physical space between humans and animals is closing up due to deforestation and population movement. Hunting of animals for bush meat, hide, horns among certain demographic populations. Expanding geographic range, civil wars forces inhabitants to seek alternative sources of protein. These form the primary reason for increasing zoonotic outbreaks. The changing climatic conditions resulting in increased rainfall and flooding forms a predisposing factor for MPX.

Monkey pox transmission

Monkey pox is a minor form of small pox, caused by variola virus, both belonging to orthopox viruses, verified not only by the similarity in their clinical signs but also their genomic constitution. These viruses possess *COP-C3L* gene that encodes complement inhibiting protein. An orthologue of this gene, present in the MPX genome, encodes monkey pox inhibitor of complement enzymes (MOPICE). Interestingly, this gene is absent in the WA clade, which might explain its less virulent nature, leading to less inter-human transmission. The WA clade is the currently circulating clade in non-endemic countries, their low virulence might also explain the lower-case fatality (3-6%) and mortality (0%) rates (Weaver and Isaacs, 2008; WHO Factsheet, 2022). In comparison to variola, the diminished clinical signs in *MPX* are suspected to be due to deficient full-length interferon-resistance (E3L, K3L) genes in the latter (Reynolds *et al.*, 2012).

Around 18000 cases from non-endemic and 49,000 cases, globally have been reported (WHO Factsheet, 2022). The high morbidity, restricted demographic population (men who have sex with men, immunosuppressed population, children etc.) its predilection site for skin and respiratory system are areas that are yet to be explored.

Pictorial representation of spread of Monkey pox from endemic to non-endemic countries

Signs and Symptoms

Monkey pox disease, with incubation period ranging from one to three weeks presents in two phases:

- Prodromal phase called the invasion period lasting between 0–5 days characterized by fever, headache, back pain, myalgia, asthenia and Lymphadenopathy.

- Skin eruption phase that lasts up to 4 weeks, characterised by centrifugally distributed maculopapular rash on the face, palms of the hands and soles of the feet. The rash develops in to macules to papules to vesicles to pustules leading to crust formation that dry up and fall off. Mucous membranes are affected leading to bronchopneumonia, gastrointestinal distress, dehydration, encephalitis and ocular infections, resulting in permanent corneal scarring.
- Severe form of disease is more evident children and patients with underlying immune deficiencies (WHO Factsheet, 2022).

Diagnosis

- Based clinical signs the disease is to be differentiated from other rash based diseases, such as chickenpox, measles, bacterial skin infections, scabies, syphilis, and medication-associated allergies. Apparent lymphadenopathy in prodromal monkey pox differentiates from chicken pox.
- Laboratory diagnosis through samples collected from skin lesions –roof or fluid from vesicles, pustules and dry crusts. Serological tests such as Immunoglobulin M (IgM) antibody assay, whole-virus enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), where antibody titers to monkeypox and vaccinia viruses are measured and ratio determined. Molecular assays that target amplification of COP-B5R gene and DNA sequencing (WHO Factsheet, 2022).

Control strategies

- Therapeutically, oral antivirals such as brincidofovir and tecovirimat, approved smallpox treatment are suggested for monkey pox control along with supportive and symptomatic treatment.
- Small pox vaccination, characterised by a scar on the upper arm offers cross protective antibodies against monkey pox disease, resulting in a milder illness. A new vaccine based on a modified attenuated vaccinia virus (Ankara strain) was approved for the prevention of monkey pox in 2019.
- Epidemiological surveillance through genome sequencing to understand temporal and spatial genetic differences in viral strains, in the two clades, to understand the pattern of disease spread.

- Identifying reservoir hosts and disease transmission patterns among them. Unprotected contact with wild animals, sick or dead, their meat, blood or other parts is to be avoided. Meat is to be thoroughly cooked prior to eating. Regulating importation of wild animals, rodents, non-human primates and their trade.
- Raising awareness and training of laboratory personnel, health care workers, rapid response teams and strengthening of national laboratory capacity in countries with endemic disease through reference laboratories.
- Screening of travellers for antibody titers and clinical symptoms prior to journey (WHO Factsheet, 2022).

Conclusion

Monkey pox is a re-emerging zoonoses, once endemic to tropical rainforests of Central and Western Africa. Its recent surge in European and Asian countries is alarming, emphasizing the need to understand its transmission and epidemiological patterns and embrace collaborative control strategies.

References

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